

Formalizing Theories of Human Behavior in Agent-Based Modeling of Transport Systems

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Abstract

Human behavior is at the basis of current societal challenges and, at the same time, of potential ways to address them. Understanding and representing it in models is therefore important. Agent-based modeling offers potential for detailed consideration of human behavior. However, the implementation of social science theories of human behavior in ABM is hampered by the fact that these theories are generally formulated in natural language, leaving room for interpretation. Formal definitions of theories that could be taken and filled in with model-specific detail in ABM implementations are lacking. To address this gap, we formalize five such theories, that is, we interpret and translate them into mathematical formulae. To ground this formalization process in an application, we present a simplified version of a large-scale agent-based model, developed to analyze potential sustainability transition scenarios in the transport sector. In this setting, we provide a comprehensive overview of all the steps taken to arrive at theory-driven decision modules. The results hence do not only allow for comparison of structures found in theories. They shall also serve as a transparent starting point for formalizations of such theories, which can be reused in other models.

Keywords: Agent-Based Modeling (ABM), Human Behavior Modeling, Formalization, Human Decision-Making, Mathematical Modeling, Social Simulation, Transport

1 Introduction

Global environmental change represents one of the most pressing challenges now and in the near future, leading to problems such as temperature rise, increased occurrence of extreme weather events, air and water pollution, loss of biodiversity and so forth (IPCC 2023). Human activities, such as burning fossil fuels, industrial processes and transportation, are the primary driver of global environmental change. Their profound and lasting impact on the environment defines the current epoch, referred to as the Anthropocene. Human behavior acts as both a significant destructive force and a lever for potential solutions. However, navigating pro-environmental change in human behavior at a societal level is complex. It requires a deeper understanding of human behavior itself and of resulting dynamics at the societal level (Steffen et al. 2008; Schill et al. 2019; Constantino et al. 2021).

One approach that fosters such understanding is social simulation; computational models are developed to capture the evolution of a system over time, while considering and integrating the relevant social behavior of humans. Different scenarios with varying conditions are explored and analyzed by adjusting relevant parameters of the model (Jager 2017; Macal 2016). Agent-based modeling (ABM) is a particularly promising methodology, which comes with the advantage of implementing autonomous agents (e.g., humans, households, companies, etc.) as individual entities with varying decision-making processes, allowing each entity to make decisions based on their own circumstances (Macal 2016). Capturing the heterogeneity of a population and discovering the emergence of macro-level phenomena from micro-level interactions are particularly interesting features of ABM (Macal and North 2010).

Viewed "with both enthusiasm and optimism due to its potential to create a 'revolution' among the social, ecological, behavioral and complexity sciences" (An et al. 2023), ABM has experienced broad popularity and a wide distribution (An et al. 2021). At the same time, ABM comes with challenges, including calibration and validation procedures, computational efficiency, transparency and reusability, and, most importantly in the given context, adequate modeling of human behavior (Huang et al. 2022; An et al. 2021; Balke and Gilbert 2014). Yet, while some of these challenges are specific to ABM, many are generally present in complex systems modeling (An et al. 2021). Further insights on challenges in ABM are discussed by: Macal (2016); Kagho et al. (2020); Huang et al. (2022); An et al. (2021); Jager (2017); Schlüter et al. (2017).

Adequate modeling of human behavior is difficult, so there are many models that use ad hoc or oversimplified approaches, which weakens the models' validity and quality (An et al. 2021). Yet, realizing more sophisticated approaches is challenging, for example due to the sheer number of available options at each step of the design process that makes it challenging to evaluate, compare and choose the most suitable approach (Schwarz et al. 2020; Polhill and Gotts 2017; Muelder and Filatova 2018).

In this paper, we focus on theories from the social sciences which deal with human decision-making. For brevity, we will refer to them as social theories in the following. As social theories are formulated primarily in natural language, they necessarily remain ambiguous. This leaves room for interpretation when a social theory is to be used in a computational model. It is hence demanding to interpret and translate a social theory for implementation in an ABM code, and there is no standardized process for doing so (e.g., Bronson and Jacobson 1990; Schwarz et al. 2020; Schlüter et al. 2017; Muelder and Filatova 2018).

While prior research considers the formalization of social theories desirable and has explored ways to clarify, simplify and standardize the formalization process (e.g. Jager et al. 2000; Schlüter et al. 2017; Scholz et al. 2023), even the term "formalization" can be interpreted in different ways, referring e.g., to graphical representations or an ABM's code. In this paper, we interpret formalization as translation into mathematical language, i.e., formulae together with natural language descriptions of their interpretations (Suppes 1968). To systematically address the gap between social theories and their implementation in ABM, we elaborate mathematical definitions for a set of five social theories. We argue that mathematical formalization can be particularly helpful in that it combines the benefits of both graphical representations and (ABM) implementations – generality and precision. While a graphical representation does well at describing general structures, it is usually not fully precise, and while an implementation in ABM code is very precise, it is necessarily case-specific. Mathematics can describe general structures precisely by providing formulae and stating requirements for them, as we hope to show below. For illustration purposes, we also provide graphical representations of our formalizations.

As duly noted throughout the literature, "translating all verbal theories, in all possible contexts, to ABMs remains impossible" (Grimm et al. 2024), theories aim at generality and details will always depend on the model context (Antosz et al. 2023; Schwarz et al. 2020). To provide such a context, without which an attempt at formalization would probably turn out void, we formalize the social theories for an example application: decision-making on mobility tool ownership. This setting is derived from a large-scale ABM on sustainable mobility, the Mobility Transition Model (MoTMo), developed to support discussions about sustainable mobility transitions in Germany (Wolf et al. 2023).

Note that we leave an investigation as to which theories are most adequate in this particular context to further work. Here, the topic of mobility choice is presented in a strongly simplified ABM setting so as to not distract by context detail. The focus is on the process with which we arrive at mathematical formalizations of the social theories selected. In this process, we aim to point out which elements of the formulae are context-specific and which refer to the general structure of (our interpretation of) the social theories. This shall allow adapting the formulae to other contexts by replacing the relevant parts with the corresponding elements from other contexts. While the description of the formalization process may seem overly detailed at first sight, we deliberately discuss all steps, hoping that this work might serve as an orientation, inspiration and transparent resource for other models.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 sketches the state of the art in the representation of human behavior in ABM, Section 3 introduces the method of mathematical formalization and makes the case for it in this context. Before we apply this method, in Section 5, to different social theories, Section 4 introduces the simple example model that these theories are embedded in. Section 6 discusses learnings and results before Section 7 concludes and gives an outlook on future research.

2 Human Behavior in Computational Models

Understanding human behavior, let alone developing theories or explicit formalizations, remains a challenge, as human behavior is complex, ambiguous, and hard to validate (Schwarz et al. 2020). At the same time, a better understanding has great potential for valuable insights and to support decision- or policy-making that concerns human-environment interactions (Schlüter et al. 2017). Computational models are an important tool for approaching this challenge and, in particular, ABMs, which allow setting a focus on human behavior, are promising (An et al. 2021). They are hence of interest in a broad variety of disciplines and studied intensively as understanding human behaviors is a priority for many research disciplines (An et al. 2023; Macal 2016). Yet, many ABMs are implemented using very limited approaches to modeling human behavior, due to missing best practices and a shared common ground, so that they lack theoretical foundations or validity when compared to the real-world (Huang et al. 2022; Mehdizadeh et al. 2022).

Recent literature (Mehdizadeh et al. 2022; Zhou et al. 2022; Schlüter et al. 2017; Balke and Gilbert 2014; An 2012) suggests the following higher-level categories of approaches relevant to this work: Simplistic approaches like ‘unspecific’, rule-driven, or heuristic-based approach are often criticized for being too simple. In the case of heuristic-based approaches, researchers typically “start with their own intuitions about human behavior in a given task and then build in mechanisms that explain additional aspects of the data” (Kuperwajs et al. 2023) leading to decision modules which follow simple rules, e.g., using thresholds for defining decisions (Huang et al. 2022). This restricts the ability to generalize the insights gained to a broader set of models. Data-driven approaches, for example artificial neural networks as described by An et al. (2023), are comparatively new and substantially different compared to the other approaches, because human behavior is implicitly derived from data and not explicitly defined (An et al. 2023). While promising, these approaches are out of scope for this work as we focus on gaining insights about the underlying details of behavioral mechanisms of individuals.

Theory-driven approaches serve as the main focus of this work and are considered promising, in that they constrain how agent behavior is implemented, reducing the danger of ad-hoc modeling decisions (Antosz et al. 2023), yet standardized best practices remain to be established. Given the heterogeneous community of agent-based modelers coming from different backgrounds (An et al. 2021), it is hard to come up with accessible and feasible practices. In fact, as of now, researchers often adopt a theory-driven approach that is significantly influenced by their own disciplinary background. Economists tend to use a rational actor approach with utility maximization, while social scientists prefer theories which are rooted in (cognitive) psychology, anthropology and sociology (Klabunde and Willekens 2016). Navigating theories outside one’s own discipline can be challenging, as a shared ‘lingua franca’ for ABMs and decision modules is still evolving within interdisciplinary research (Grimm et al. 2020). This might lead to misunderstandings, as terms and theories often differ or overlap subtly and not necessarily consistently across fields, creating another layer of difficulty in integrating theory-driven approaches effectively (Grimm et al. 2020).

Jäger (2017) states two major challenges when implementing theory-driven approaches: (1) identification of relevant theories, and (2) a lack of formalization. (1) is addressed by a variety of work, which helps researchers find the right theory for their model. Balke and Gilbert (2014) present a review of 14 agent decision-making architectures. Schlüter et al. (2017) introduce the MoHuB (Modeling Human Behaviour) framework for mapping and comparing behavioral theories and expand on it with the successor HuB-CC (Human Behavior-Cognition in Context) as presented by Constantino et al. (2021), a process-oriented framework of embedded human cognition. Groeneveld et al. (2017) examine theoretical foundations of human decision-making in agent-based land use models. Mehdizadeh et al. (2022) conduct a similar review for the mobility sector, Mooij et al. (2023) for epidemiology and Klabunde and Willekens (2016) for migration. Wijermans et al. (2023) and Antosz et al. (2023) adopt a meta-level perspective, respectively, discussing the broader justification for the suitability of decision models, and analyzing roles of theory in ABMs and ABMs for theory. Thus, while several studies offer overviews, still comparing them proves challenging due to their origins in different disciplines. A rich but fragmented landscape of theory-driven approaches in ABMs (Schlüter et al. 2017) hence remains.

While challenge (1) is systematically addressed through the development of the listed frameworks, when using the insights gained from them, a modeler is confronted with challenge (2), the lack of formalization, an area that has received comparatively less attention. The present paper addresses this gap by formalizing five social theories in an example context. For the selection of theories, we refer to Schlüter et al. (2017), who base their choice six theories – from which we drop the theory

of planned behavior¹ – from a pool of about 30 on representing a broad spectrum of both human behavioral drivers and usage in different scientific disciplines. This results in the list of rational choice theory, bounded rationality, reinforcement learning, prospect theory, and descriptive norms. With explicit formalizations in mathematical terms, we go beyond previous work.

3 The Method of Mathematical Formalization

Formalization refers to the translation of concepts or a theory, expressed in natural language, into some kind of formal language. This may be pseudo-code, graphical representations such as decision trees or flow charts (e.g., Schwarz et al. 2020), or mathematical language. The latter includes formulae but also natural language description of what each piece of notation represents. Strictly speaking, a formalization of a theory should remain as general as the theory itself. While related, this is not identical to modeling, which refers to the process of simplifying a given real-world situation, translating the result into mathematics, obtaining a result within mathematics, translating this result back to the real-world situation to check whether the model fits. If so, conclusions for the real-world situation can be drawn, if not, the process starts anew (Blum and Leiß 2007). This process means that a model always presupposes and application context. In an (idealized) modeling process, two steps have been identified. In the context of (aggregate rather than agent-based) modeling of change in informal social norms, Bronson and Jacobson (1990) suggest that first, an unambiguous and general definition of a social theory is needed, and second, an empirical indicator that can be used to measure it has to be identified. This second step is also known as an operational definition or operationalization of the concept (e.g. de Finetti 1974).

The translation of a theory into (a part of) an ABM then involves two aspects: on the one hand, a theory is supposed to be general by definition and hence can never provide all the details needed when developing a model in a specific context (Antosz et al. 2023), on the other hand, natural language always leaves room for interpretation requiring further specification from a modeler. In fact, much of the above cited literature agrees on the fact that social theories, described using natural language, pose challenges for modelers: they "experience some ambiguities" or are "not complete" (Schlüter et al. 2017), or "provide far less detail than what is required for a simulation model" (Schwarz et al. 2020).

Ideally, one might associate the formalization of a social theory with providing an unambiguous and general definition, i.e., further specifying what a natural language definition leaves ambiguous. An operational definition would then be associated with specifying the theory to a particular model context. However, in practice, these aspects cannot be neatly separated. When moving from a general, abstract description of concepts and relations between them to a specific implementation of an ABM code for a given system under study, making a natural language definition more precise and specifying it to a concrete case are two sides of the same coin. Both a precise definition and its operationalization in a given context require subjective decisions by a modeler – creativity even (Muelder and Filatova 2018). This naturally leads to a multitude of varying and case-specific uses of social theories in ABM.

Previous literature has defined general structures of social theories in an abstract setting (e.g., Schlüter et al. 2017) or has abstracted back from details given by case-specific ABM codes definitions, finding commonalities but also differences in structures, a paramount example is the work by Muelder and Filatova (2018) for the theory of planned behavior. What is rarely done in ABM development, is to provide a formal definition of the social theory used as an intermediate step between the social theory and the ABM code – more precise than the natural language definition, but more general than the code. This paper illustrates this intermediate step through example formalizations and aims to show how mathematics can help to be explicit about assumptions made (Suppes 1968) – a point considered important in previous literature (e.g., by Schlüter et al. 2017). Note that we do not suggest to rephrase a whole ABM in mathematical terms – ABM are used precisely when a description of some dynamics in terms of an overseable set of equations is not possible (Secchi et al. 2024) – but want to clearly phrase small elements in an ABM to make these precise and unambiguous. This also means that mathematical knowledge beyond high school is not necessary for reading Sections 4 and 5: we do not employ mathematical results but only use rather basic concepts (such as functions) for describing pieces of ABMs.

¹This theory has been thoroughly discussed in the context of ABM in previous works (see, e.g., Muelder and Filatova 2018; Aizen and Klobas 2013; Klabunde et al. 2015). Its high degree of elaboration might lead to confusing rather than illuminating results when combined with the (overly) simplistic model used here.

As in the case of TPB mentioned above, where there is not a single "correct" formalization, the examples provided here will be based on interpretations of the social theories – in this case our interpretations and in this sense also on the chosen context. Many other formalizations can exist, and in particular, in other contexts others may be more fitting. Based on the interpretations chosen here, we can then illustrate similarities, differences, and connections between the theories.

Building on previous (frame)works (Schlüter et al. 2017; Wijermans et al. 2023; Müller et al. 2013), and their definitions and categorizations of concepts commonly found across social theories, we aim to make assumptions explicit with the help of mathematical definitions. In these, one can state requirements or conditions (such as which kinds of inputs a function should take to produce which kind of outputs, or that it should have some specific form) while leaving open details that have to be filled in case-by-case (such as which concrete function is to be used, as this may depend on the context). The approach may be seen as complementary to the set of tasks to guide modelers in the formalization process described by Schwarz et al. (2020), who emphasize that they do not provide off-the-shelf formalizations. While an actual off-the-shelf, plug-and-play system of blocks of code for assembling ABMs will remain impossible due to the necessity of context adaptation, we provide example formulae that may provide a structure for modelers to complete with context specific detail for their ABMs. Also, using mathematical definitions, the remaining step from these formalizations to ABM code implementations can be smaller than the step from, e.g., graphically displayed information to code. In this sense, we provide a form of reusable building blocks, that "can be seen as a recipe or algorithm for describing a process, rather than a fixed block of code restricted to a particular programming language" (Berger et al. 2024, p.2). Proposing these formalizations, we aim to clarify assumptions and to offer "some level of generalization" (a goal expressed by Antosz et al. 2023, in the related context of how ABM can support theory development).

The development of well-defined formalizations of social theories, accompanied by distinguishable terminology for their variations, would contribute to establishing a shared scientific language or a 'lingua franca' (Grimm et al. 2020), as then such formalizations can enable precise and consistent discussions of shared concepts. Ideally, formalizations of social theories would be developed with an interdisciplinary team of modelers, psychologists, and social scientists in a continuous, iterative process consisting of definition, validation, updating the definition, validation, etc.² We hope that the formalizations proposed here can support or even serve as a starting point in such a process.

4 Formalization Applied – The Example Model

Before formalizing the above listed theories in the context of mobility decisions (Section 5), we will briefly set the context of the model (Section 4.1), sketch the ABM that the decision modules are embedded into (Section 4.2), and define decision module elements for later use (Section 4.3). Thus illustrating the process of formalizing social theories in the context of a specific but purposefully simple ABM and describing challenges encountered, we hope to support similar formalizations in other models. In the ABM literature, this process of design and formal definition is frequently not explicitly displayed, sometimes hindering full comprehension, transparency and reproducibility of decision modules used.

4.1 Context of the Mobility ABM

The present work aims to refine the Mobility Transition Model (MoTMo) that simulates alternative scenarios over a few decades in view of sustainable mobility transitions (Wolf et al. 2023); in particular, within the overall model structure, the agents' decision module is to be redefined. Mobility decisions and behavior impact sustainability through global factors, such as CO₂ emissions and energy consumption, as well as local factors, including space consumption, air pollution, social equity, and accessibility. Here, we focus on global factors and on people's daily mobility. Air travel and long-distance public transportation (PT) depend on a very different behavioral context and are therefore beyond the scope of this work. Emissions resulting from human mobility behavior depend on the mode of transport. In Table 1, emissions by mode of transport for Germany in 2017 are listed as published by

²The term "validation" here needs to be taken with a grain of salt: as pointed out by Antosz et al. (2023), "any conclusions about theories put into an ABM is relative to a host of other added assumptions" that are part of the model itself. We will come back to this in the discussion in Section 6.

the German Federal Environment Agency (Allekotte et al. 2021), where passenger-kilometers account for the capacity and occupancy of a transport vehicle.

Transport mode	Emissions (g CO _{2eq} /Pkm)	Number of trips (%)	Climate impact (%)
Walking	0	20.1	0.0
Cycling	9.16	10.1	0.2
Public transport (local)	73.69 – 88.63	12.2	3.6
Public transport (long-distance)	31.62 – 46.32	0.2	1.5
Motorized individual transport	194.41	57.3	75.3
Flying	197,51 – 218.12	0.1	19.4

Table 1: Emissions and modal shares by transport mode in Germany in 2017. For more detailed information, please refer to Tables 2 and 3 in Allekotte et al. (2021).

Motorized individual transport has the highest emission rates in road traffic and combined with its popularity, 75,3% of the passenger transport emissions are caused by motorized individual transport. Walking and cycling have very little emissions. Due to the important contribution of motorized individual transport to the overall emissions, this mode is the main focus of the decision module for now. While additional emissions result from the production of transport vehicles, with those associated with motorized individual transport being considerably higher than those of other transport modes, these are again beyond the scope of this work.

The most significant factor for using motorized individual transport or an alternative is the availability (Schmid et al. 2023). For motorized individual transport, the availability is defined by the car ownership status. Car ownership in turn leads to a car-centered mobility style as thoroughly investigated by Hausteil and Hunecke (2007, 2013); Hausteil and Kroesen (2022). Also, due to a car’s lifetime, the attribute car ownership has to be analyzed in the long term, which aligns with the scope of MoTMo. We therefore concentrate on the decision-making process for car ownership here. In ongoing work, MoTMo is combined with the Multi-Agent Transport Simulation MATSim (Horni et al. 2016) for additionally modeling the more detailed daily decision-making on mode usage.

Decisions about car ownership are based on many different factors; an overview is given in Table 2 (based on Hausteil and Kroesen 2022; Gu et al. 2021; Schmid et al. 2023), categorized and sorted in preparation of the formalization process. Evidently, the large number of factors is challenging. In addition, many factors are difficult to quantify or measure, and some are interdependent or based on multiple sub-factors themselves. To avoid these complications here, we focus on geographical and financial aspects for the following reasons: First, these factors are among the most significant ones (Hausteil and Kroesen 2022; Gu et al. 2021; Schmid et al. 2023). Second, a minimal selection of clearly distinguishable factors is made to avoid interdependence between the factors used. For example, social factors such as status or prestige might depend on financial factors as the socio-economic status. Third, the decision module is kept as simple as possible to clearly illustrate similarities and differences between the social theories considered.

4.2 Main Aspects of the Mobility Transition Model

To provide the relevant context for the formalization of social theories, we outline relevant aspects of MoTMo in their simplest possible expression along the lines of the ODD protocol’s overview section (Grimm et al. 2020). Hence, we first present the model’s *purpose and patterns*: MoTMo is developed to model mobility behavior and patterns spanning multiple decades, to enhance the understanding of daily human mobility in the long term under various policy settings. Its purpose is to provide insights into system dynamics in support of discussions and informed decision-making by policy-makers, stakeholders and citizens (Wolf et al. 2023). Patterns to be reproduced by the model are the past evolution of numbers of privately owned vehicles in the study regions (as provided by KBA (2025)) as well as insights and attributes about the population’s mobility choices as obtained from the *Mobilität in Deutschland* (MiD) survey studies (BMDV 2018).

Factor	Description
Personal and Household Factors	Age, gender, household size and composition, educational level, occupation, <i>mobility milestones</i> (life events impacting mobility behavior)
Actual Mobility Behavior	Actual mobility behavior, which is currently performed
Activity Schedule Demands	Depending on personal schedule: Number of trips, distance traveled, travel time considerations, etc.
Economic Factors	Fixed and operational costs of transport modes (depending on socio-economic status based on wealth and income level)
Geographic and Infrastructure Factors	Availability, accessibility, safety, and quality of transport modes (depending on home location)
Social Factors	Status/prestige, responsibility for others, expectations/pressure by others depending on cultural norms or socio-economic status group
Psychological Factors	Personality-based preferences impacting curiosity for new technologies, driving fun/passion, alignment with lifestyle, perceived freedom/autonomy, convenience, environmental considerations, risk aversion, consistency in habits and routines
Regulatory Factors	Incentives and restrictions enacted by the government

Table 2: Overview of relevant decision factors for car ownership

Second, we sketch *entities, state variables, and scales* of the model, where we refer to the entities’ state variables as attributes in the following:

- As part of the environment in the model, the available transport modes are considered entities in the model. While they do not have agency, they differ among each other and might undergo changes throughout a model simulation. An example attribute (that can vary, e.g., through policy interventions) is their cost, denoted $c \in \mathbb{R}_+$. To start with the simplest possible model, we consider just two modes, **car** and **other**, where the latter summarizes public transport, cycling and walking. For notational convenience below, we define the set of modes to be $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{car}, \text{other}\}$ and refer to modes as $m \in \mathcal{M}$.
- A second kind of entities in the model are its spatial units, that we refer to as locations $l \in \mathcal{L} = \{l_1, \dots, l_L\}$, where \mathcal{L} denotes the number of locations in a given context. We consider locations that are cells in a given grid, in other models, one might also use administrative units (quarters in a city, etc.), or any kind of polygons adapted to a specific context. As we will not use the cells’ position in the grid here, their only attribute is a spatial type $r \in R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_7\}$ as defined by (?)’s, regional statistical spatial typology. We consider 7 different spatial types (4 in urban and 3 in rural areas) and the spatial type of a specific location l_j is denoted $r(l_j)$.
- Finally, the model contains one type of agents: a set $H = \{h_1, \dots, h_n\}$ of $n \in \mathbb{N}$ humans or private persons. While households play a role in MoTMO, we abstract from them here for simplicity. The agents’ attributes include their mobility toolbox, $b \in \{0, 1\}$, where 1 indicates car ownership and 0 indicates that no car is owned by the agent; recall that we abstract from the availability of other modes here – for simplicity, we consider these available for all agents – and note that we also disregard the possibility of owning more than one car per agent. Agents’ further attributes are a home location $l \in \mathcal{L}$ and a socio-economic status $s \in S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_5\}$, where we refer to the five status groups as defined by MiD (BMDV 2018) from very low to very high. As before, the attributes of an agent h_k will be denoted $b(h_k)$, $l(h_k)$, or $s(h_k)$, respectively.

As scales of the model, we can consider its spatial and temporal extensions: geospatially, two study regions determine the locations included in the model; the temporal horizon of the model is three decades (2015-2045) with a quarterly time step; however, these scales are of minor interest for the present paper.

Third, the ODD’s element *process overview and scheduling* is not of interest here either, as instead of looking at the whole model, we here restrict the focus to a specific decision by agents. When

scheduling within the decision-making process is concerned, this will be addressed in the formalizations of social theories below (Section 5). Other processes, such as feedback between decisions and other model components, or exogenously induced dynamics, like changes in infrastructure or prices, will be addressed in further work.

4.3 Defining Decision Module Elements

To specify decision modules according to the given theories below, we first define elements that all or many of these modules have in common, based on general elements identified in previous work. The most fundamental point seems to be Müller et al. (2013)'s question as to *subjects* and *objects* of decision-making, where in the context of an ABM the subjects are agents, but objects can vary. Schlüter et al. (2017); Wijermans et al. (2023); Müller et al. (2013) further categorize elements in the agents' states, such as goals, values, knowledge and assets, but we skip further detail on agents' states here, as for our simple setting, their state has been defined above. The object of an agent's decision-making in our case is one of its own state variables (as car ownership is given by its mobility toolbox *b*). Section 4.3.4 explicitly defines the set of options between which agents decide.

Next, Muelder and Filatova (2018) start from the premise that human decision-making is a multi-stage process, and in fact, several such stages are discussed in the literature. In particular, distinctions are made between which criteria to include in a decision and how to select a behavioral option (as described by Schwarz et al. 2020), or the aspects included into the decision-making and the decision-making representation (e.g., a utility function or IF-THEN rules as formulated by Wijermans et al. 2023), or whether agents have some types of success criteria, and how they pursue these (Müller et al. 2013). These distinctions can be summarized in the terms *evaluation* and *selection* that Schlüter et al. (2017) categorize as the agent's internal processes in decision-making. The prime example in terms of evaluation is the concept of utility, that we will discuss for our context in Sections 4.3.1 to 4.3.3. Examples of selection mechanisms abound in the cited literature, including random choice, optimization, imitation of other agents, satisficing, and more, with different variants of many of these mechanisms. Whether and how an evaluation is used in some selection mechanism is then formalized according to the given social theories in Section 5.

A final remark before moving to the definition of decision module elements: it is often pointed out that modelers should specify whether and how spatial as well as temporal aspects and uncertainty are included in decision-making (see, e.g., Müller et al. 2013; Schwarz et al. 2020). In our case, spatial aspects will figure in the utility function as defined below, and we abstract from uncertainty and all but the simplest temporal aspects, i.e., agents have no memory of the past nor expectations about the future here. We will point to this where applicable in the following.

4.3.1 Utility and decision criteria

As the term *evaluation* suggests, in this step of decision-making, different alternatives are equipped with a *value* that makes them comparable. A standard tool for doing so is the concept utility, that provides abstract utility values, usually real numbers, which do not necessarily say much in themselves but are comparable in that the terms smaller, larger, equal are well-defined. Utility originates in economics and is strongly tied to the rational actor theory, which is among the formalized theories below. In fact, it formalizes the evaluation step in this theory. In the case where decision-making concerns a finite set of alternatives (as is the case for our example of car ownership), often discrete choice theory is used, where a statistical approach is taken to model how agents' attributes translate to probabilities of choosing each alternative. We nevertheless consider utility here, so as to make the evaluation step explicit.

In the most basic case, a utility function represents an agent's preferences over a finite set of alternatives $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$. In a decision situation, these alternatives may correspond to the decision options, so that $X = \mathcal{O}$, but this need not be the case. The preferences are considered given and denoted, e.g., \preceq , that is, $x_i \preceq x_j$ means that the agent considers x_j at least as desirable as x_i . If a preference ordering fulfills the conditions of reflexivity, completeness, and transitivity³, it can be

³Reflexivity means that each option is at least as preferred as itself. Completeness means that any two options can be compared by the preference ordering. Transitivity means that if $x_i \preceq x_j$ and $x_j \preceq x_k$, then also $x_i \preceq x_k$. With these conditions, a preference ordering is called rational.

represented by a utility function $u : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that fulfills:

$$\text{for any } x_i, x_j \in X : u(x_i) \leq u(x_j) \Leftrightarrow x_i \preceq x_j,$$

in words, a utility function represents the ordering by assigning real numbers to each element in a set, where a larger number expresses a larger preference (Debreu 1954). Since utility functions are easier to work with than the underlying preference orderings, they are widely used.

In the context of consumption, that is a prominent topic in economics, utility functions are often used to express preferences over bundles of goods, assuming that these goods are infinitely divisible, i.e., their amount can be any real number. We denote the amount of each good in a bundle as a vector $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for the case of n goods. While the general assumption on goods is that 'more is better', it is not a priori clear how to compare two bundles where one has more of a first good, but the other one contains more of a second good. The evaluation depends on the preferences of an agent that are again expressed via a utility function. In this case, the utility function provides an aggregation of the amounts of all goods into one value, $u : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

The same idea of utility as aggregation can be applied in more general cases to express an aggregation of several criteria into one value. For example, in the mobility context, criteria to evaluate a transport mode may include time needed, costs, convenience, etc. Note that for some criteria, such as time needed and costs, the standard assumption would be 'less is better', but this can be taken care of.

Two very common examples of utility functions that provide such aggregations are (i) a weighted sum of criteria and the corresponding multiplicative formula, which is (ii) a weighted product of criteria, where weighting is obtained using exponents; the latter is known as the Cobb-Douglas utility function. Many other functions can be used, expressing various assumptions about preferences. In addition, in settings with uncertainty, the concept is usually extended to the expected utility. We will not go further into these topics here.

In the following, we use (i) as a simple example and consider just two criteria – representing convenience and cost of modes, as these link to the geographical and financial decision factors chosen above – to define the utility function.

4.3.2 Decision Factors

Given the two decision criteria convenience and costs, we need to operationalize them, i.e., define what is measured for each of the criteria. To denominate this, we borrow the term *decision factors*, that is not generally used in previous (frame)works on social theories in ABM to our knowledge, from the literature on mobility decisions as described in Section 4.1.

While decision-making is considered from the perspective of an individual agent, such decision factors may also derive from other model entities and their attributes, as long as these can be mapped to the individual agent. For example, a decision factor may depend on a spatial location, so that an agent inherits it via its home location. Here, we define just two example decision factors to keep it simple and clear:

- In view of the convenience criterion, a spatially explicit infrastructure score is defined for each transport mode, where for simplicity we abstract from the single locations, but consider the infrastructure score as depending on the regional statistic type of locations (see 4.2). Also for simplicity, infrastructure scores are defined to lie in $I = [0, 1]$, with the interpretation that a higher infrastructure score indicates a better quality of infrastructure.⁴ For agent h_k , the relevant infrastructure score values for the two modes are those of the region type of its home location: $i(r(l(h_k)), m)$. As this becomes hard to read, we abbreviate and define: $i(h_k, m) := i(r(l(h_k)), m)$
- Similarly, the financial load of each transport mode experienced by an agent will depend not only on the transport mode's cost $c(m)$ but also on the agent's socio-economic status. We define the financial load f a function of the socio-economic status and the mode, $f : S \times \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow B$ with $B = [0, 1]$. In the model implementation, its values for the 10 possible combinations (of 2 modes and 5 status groups) are determined from data. At an abstract level, we require the function to be increasing in the cost and decreasing in the social status component, while a concrete definition of the function will have to be tested and possibly changed in the model validation step. From

⁴In MoTMO, these scores are derived from survey data, but the details are not important here.

the agent’s perspective, the relevant values are those corresponding to the agent’s socio-economic status, $f(s(h_k), c(m))$, which we analogously abbreviate: $f(h_k, m) := f(s(h_k), c(m))$

This specification of decision factors illustrates how mathematical formalization helps make explicit assumptions at a more general level than via a concrete ABM implementation. As done for the financial load, also the infrastructure score can be written as a function of region type and mode, $i : R \times \mathcal{M} \rightarrow I$. Further properties that this function should have in order to be a useful representation of an infrastructure score could be specified and/or discussed at an abstract level. We skip such a discussion here, since it would need to go too deeply into the definition of the regional statistical spatial typology used, e.g., to decide how a specific urban type relates to a specific rural one. However, clarifying structures at this abstract level constitutes an intermediate step between a concept description and an example implementation in an ABM – and this is one of the benefits of mathematical formalization.

Table 3 lists an agent’s decision factors and how these result from its state and attributes of related entities in the model. As will be seen, the agent’s car ownership status and the utility of both modes are also part of decision-making in the theories formalized below. The latter is calculated in the following section.

Notation	Description	Values
b_t	Mobility toolbox, i.e. car ownership status, at the time of decision-making	$\{0, 1\}$
$s(h_k)$	Socio-economic status based on income (from low to high)	$S = \{1,2,3,4,5\}$
$c(m)$	Cost of mode	\mathbb{R}_+
$f(h_k, m)$	Financial load of each transport mode depending on socio-economic status $s(h_k)$ and cost of mode $c(m)$ as defined above	For (Car,Other): \mathbb{R}^2
$r(l(h_k))$	Region type of home location	$R = \{1,2,3,4,5,6,7\}$
$i(h_k, m)$	Infrastructure score of each transport mode depending on region type of home location $r(l(h_k))$ as defined above	For (Car,Other): \mathbb{R}^2
$u(m)$	Resulting utility of each transport mode	For (Car,Other): \mathbb{R}^2

Table 3: Overview of an agent’s decision factors and necessary related information from the model. Elements in gray are used implicitly to determine others and are hence not explicitly used in the formalizations below.

4.3.3 Utility of Transport Modes

Using all of the above, we define an example utility function, with which each agent $h_k \in H$ can evaluate the individual utility of the transport modes $m \in \mathcal{M} = \{\text{car}, \text{other}\}$:

$$u_{h_k}(m) = \alpha_1 i(h_k, m) + \alpha_2 b(h_k, m), \quad (1)$$

where weights $\alpha_1 > 0$ and $\alpha_2 < 0$ reflect the assumptions that the utility of a mode increases with a higher quality of infrastructure and decreases with the associated financial load. The explicit values of these weights need to be defined in the implementation of the model, obtained via calibration to real-world data. In the implementation of the large-scale mobility ABM MoTMO, the utility calculation will be extended with further criteria, respectively decision factors to increase realism. A relatively straightforward extension might be to vary the values of the weights between agents, to represent that people can weight the criteria differently. This could be based on data for groups of agents (e.g., if data suggest that agents who have to transport kids might put a larger weight on convenience or similar) and/or by random perturbations to summarily represent heterogeneity in agents’ preferences. However, to minimize complexity in this work, this simple form is used in the following.

4.3.4 Decision Options

As described above, among the two kinds of mobility decisions – relating to ownership/availability and usage of transport modes – we focus on the former and assume, for simplicity, that except for cars

all other transport modes are always available. Hence, it is sufficient to consider the agents' decision between the two alternatives of owning a car and not owning a car. For a given agent, the set of options to decide between can be written in two ways: focusing on resulting car ownership status, the options are:

- o_1 : the agent decides to own a car, i.e. the mobility toolbox is maintained or changed to $b = 1$
- o_2 : the agent decides to not own a car, i.e. the mobility toolbox is maintained or changed to $b = 0$.

Focusing on whether the decision means a change to the agent's mobility toolbox or not, which may be the more relevant perspective, one can alternatively consider the options "buying a car", "selling a car", "keeping a car" or "remaining without car". The definition of these options is a bit more involved, as they depend on the current mobility toolbox of the agent. As soon as this is the case, time needs to be made explicit: we denote it by an index $t \in \mathbb{N}$. Thus, we distinguish the value of the agent's state variable "pre-decision" from its "post-decision" value by denoting the current status b_t and the status resulting from the decision b_{t+1} . Then, the options can be written as:

- o_3 : the agent decides to stick to the current car ownership status, i.e., the mobility toolbox is maintained, $b_{t+1} = b_t$
- o_4 : the agent decides to sell the car, i.e., if $b_t = 1$, then $b_{t+1} = 0$ (otherwise, this option is not applicable)
- o_5 : the agent decides to buy a car, i.e., if $b_t = 0$, then $b_{t+1} = 1$ (otherwise, this option is not applicable)

Note that the time indices t and $t + 1$ may or may not correspond to the time step of the model. For example, if an agent can take more than one decision within one model time step, this will not be the case. Here, the indices are meant only to represent pre- and post-decision values. For reasons that will become clear below, we will consider the set $\mathcal{O} = \{o_1, o_2, o_3\}$ as the available options for an agent's decision, although this mixes the two perspectives outlined. Based on the corresponding theory, the next section defines the process by which an option is selected.

5 Formalization Applied to Selected Theories

In this section, we use the five selected social theories – rational actor, bounded rationality, habitual or reinforcement learning, prospect theory, and descriptive norms theory – as starting points to develop theory-driven decision modules. By doing so, we elaborate prevailing structures explicitly and highlight where a formalization of the social theories requires further specifications by modelers. Contingent on the subjective interpretations used, we demonstrate similarities and differences between the theories.

The formalizations are based on elements defined in the previous section; they each provide an agent's car ownership decision. The decision process consists of (up to) two main steps, corresponding to evaluation (optional) and selection as identified in previous works. The main structure can therefore be summarized in a basic decision module, visualized in Figure 1, that constitutes a starting point for the following social theory formalizations.

5.1 Rational Actor or Homo Economicus

The main characteristics of the rational actor theory are the assumptions that an agent is perfectly informed, acts in their own self-interest, and makes consistent and logically reasoned decisions based on well-defined preferences (as described in 4.3.1). This is summarized in making decisions by maximizing utility. For a more in-depth discussion of the theory, refer to [Simon \(1955\)](#); [Frank \(1987\)](#); [Monroe \(2001\)](#); [Schlüter et al. \(2017\)](#).

In the decision module based on the rational actor theory, agents select an alternative by maximizing utility. As utilities are defined for transport modes, but the decision concerns the agents' availability of the mode `car`, the link between the evaluation in terms of utilities and the selection step has to be explicitly defined. We assume that agents' decisions are aimed at always having the transport mode

Figure 1: Basic decision module structure.

with the highest utility available, leading to the following formalization with $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{car}, \text{other}\}$ and utilities $u_{h_k}(m)$ as defined in Equation (1). We consider the mode(s) with the maximum utility,

$$m^* = \arg \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (u_{h_k}(m)) = \arg \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (\alpha_1 i(h_k, m) + \alpha_2 b(h_k, m)) \quad (2)$$

where $\arg \max$ denotes the set of values for which a function is maximal. If this contains only the mode **car**, an agent selects decision option o_1 and owns a car. If m^* contains only **other**, an agent selects decision option o_2 and does not own a car. If the utility of both modes is equal, i.e., $m^* = \mathcal{M}$, maximization alone would leave the selection step undetermined, so that the modeler needs to choose how to define the decision in this case.⁵ Given the long term nature of car ownership, we define that an agent selects decision option o_3 and sticks to the current car ownership status. In mathematical formulae, with o^* denoting the result of the decision, we get:

$$o^* = \begin{cases} o_1, & \text{IF } m^* = \{\text{car}\} \\ o_2, & \text{IF } m^* = \{\text{other}\} \\ o_3, & \text{IF } m^* = \mathcal{M}. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

5.2 Bounded Rationality

The bounded rationality theory can be seen as a modification or extension of the rational actor theory. The main characteristics of bounded rationality are that an agent still acts in their own self-interest, but due to limitations, e.g., in cognitive capacity, information availability or time, utility is not necessarily maximized. These different examples indicate that ideas behind bounding rationality are manifold, and in fact, there are numerous variants of the theory. Which interpretation is adequate in a given context is determined subjectively to a large extent. For a more in-depth discussion of the theory, refer to, [Simon \(1978\)](#); [Gigerenzer and Selten \(2001\)](#); [Schlüter et al. \(2017\)](#).

To illustrate, we consider two possible formalizations of bounded rationality. The formalizations are based on key aspects of the theory as emphasized by [Schlüter et al. \(2017\)](#). In the first formalization, agents strive for satisfaction or gratification rather than maximization of their utilities. For the formalization, we suggest to introduce a gratification threshold GT , so that if a utility exceeds GT no

⁵This is true also when utility is defined directly for the options that an agent decides between.

additional value is gained by the agent. The explicit value of such a threshold needs to be evaluated via validation in alignment with real-world data.

With $u_{h_k}(m)$ as defined in Equation (1) bounded rationality can be defined by truncating utility to the gratification threshold’s value. This means that the maximization is applied to $\min(u_{h_k}(m), GT)$ for each mode, i.e.,

$$m^* = \arg \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (\min(u_{h_k}(m), GT)) \quad (4)$$

while the selection step remains as above in Equation (3). As a result, the formalization is quite analogous to the rational actor approach (see 5.1): the same evaluation of utilities and the same definition of the final choice apply, while the only difference is in the input used in the maximization to determine m^* , thus changing (4) with respect to (2).

In the second formalization, we focus on the idea of limits in information availability and make a change in the utility evaluation step. Removing the information about the financial decision factor in Equation (1) represents the idea that agents ignore the financial load of owning a car in their decision-making process. While this might not be completely realistic, there is evidence, however, that people often underestimate this burden (Haustein and Hunecke 2007).

Formally, this can be represented by redefining the utility function so that it forgets about the financial information, i.e., an agent uses its value of the infrastructure score $i(h_k, m)$ but instead of its financial load $b(h_k, m)$ considers 0 (the neutral element in the additive utility function) as inputs to the utility function. The resulting new utility function, say a , based on the limited available information is

$$a_{h_k}(m) = u(i(h_k, m), 0) = \alpha_1 i(h_k, m). \quad (5)$$

Then, in complete analogy to (2) of the rational agent this function is used to determine m^* via

$$m^* = \arg \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (a_{h_k}(m)), \quad (6)$$

and the decision is again taken according to equation (3).

These two examples were chosen not only to illustrate different interpretations of bounded rationality but also to show that there is neither a unique way of separating between the two steps of evaluation and selection, nor necessarily a unique formal description of a specific procedure. For example, the definition of the new utility function in the second example was useful but not necessary. One could have instead redefined the agents’ decision factors to remove the information on b and replace it by 0, and then used u instead of a in the following.

As a remark on spatial and temporal aspects note that agents’ decisions for both the rational agent’s decision module and the two examples of bounded rationality depend on space via the value of i for their home location. Time was not explicitly considered due to the simplicity of the examples. On the one hand, it is assumed that the values of the decision factors are fixed rather than evolving in time. On the other hand, this setup can be considered the simplest possible form of agents’ expectations: implicitly, we assume that agents expect the utility of the modes to remain constant (Klabunde et al. 2015).

5.3 Habitual / Reinforcement Learning

The habitual/reinforcement learning⁶ theory highlights the role of habits in human behavior, suggesting that individuals rely on established patterns of behavior rather than actively evaluating the choices. The focus is on the feedback mechanism, which is driven by agents’ past experiences and the outcomes of their behavior over time. At the first decision-making instance, a behavior is considered intentional and goal-directed. This behavior becomes more and more likely, if it is reinforced by a positive outcome or becomes less likely, if it is discouraged by a negative outcome, leading to habit formation. An individual maintains this behavior as long as needs are satisfied. If the needs are no longer satisfied, the behavior might persist for some time but change eventually. For a more in-depth discussion of the theory, refer to Skinner (2019); Pavlov (1927); Graybiel (2008); Schlüter et al. (2017).

In the decision module based on habitual/reinforcement learning theory, time has to be explicitly considered to express that decisions are influenced by the currently prevailing decision or current state

⁶Note that there is a formalized version of reinforcement learning at the intersection of machine learning and optimal control. It is beyond the scope of our simplistic model here.

– and possibly by previous decisions, but we abstract from the latter for simplicity. Note that we actually included the current mobility tool ownership also in the cases above, via the choice of option o_3 , but this was acting from necessity, in order to define a decision outcome where maximization does not provide a single choice. To describe habit formation, we consider an initial decision, and hence the current car ownership status, i.e., the agent’s mobility toolbox b_t , given. An agent’s first decision about owning a car might, e.g., have been taken when a driving license was obtained, and in the model, an initial state of each agent’s mobility toolbox needs to be set. We consider the moment in time at which the agent needs to decide on car ownership at time $t + 1$, i.e. the decision taken will be denoted o_{t+1}^* . We further suggest to allow an agent to enter the decision-making process only if at least one of the following circumstances apply:

- The needs of an agent are no longer satisfied, i.e. the utility of the agent’s current car ownership status is below a gratification threshold GT just as defined in the bounded rationality approach (see 5.2).
- A mobility milestone occurs for an agent. A mobility milestone is a life event that is explicitly relevant to mobility behavior, such as obtaining a driving license, a traffic accident, a change of residence, the birth of a child, etc. For more details on the concept of mobility milestones, see (Rau and Manton 2016). From the perspective of the decision module, these milestones are exogenously given, e.g., obtained from a demographic model’s dynamics or simply probabilistically for our purposes.⁷

If at least one of the two conditions is satisfied, the agent enters the decision-making process, for which the decision-making process then has to be defined explicitly. Otherwise, no decision is taken, which can be represented formally as $o_{t+1}^* = o_3$.

$$o_{t+1}^* = \begin{cases} \hat{o}, & \text{IF } u_{h_k}(o_t^*) < GT \text{ OR a mobility milestone occurs} \\ o_3 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where \hat{o} is a placeholder for the outcome of the decision process to be defined. This can, but need not, be done through one of the examples above. Adapting Figure 1 to capture the habitual/reinforcement learning approach leads to Figure 2.

5.4 Prospect Theory

Prospect Theory, developed by Kahneman and Tversky (1979), uses the rational actor theory as a starting point and adapts the assumptions to reflect cognitive biases that Kahneman and Tversky (1979) systematically discovered and which contradict consistent rationality in people’s behavior. As a first concept, the theory highlights an irrational willingness to seek or avoid risk. ”Losses are more important than gains” (Kahneman and Tversky 1979) is one of the key conclusions that explains how individuals evaluate potential gains and losses relative to a reference point rather than universally, and how losses are evaluated more negatively than equivalent gains are evaluated positively. As a result, individuals confronted with potential gains are rather risk-seeking and individuals confronted with potential losses are rather risk-averse. Further, the theory highlights how individuals overweight unlikely events and underweight highly probable ones. The resulting main characteristics of prospect theory are different systematic cognitive biases (loss aversion, certainty effect, isolation effect and overweighting of low probabilities, reflection effect, etc.) that influence an individual’s decision-making, often leading to irrational and inconsistent choices. Note that different cognitive biases are systematic modifications of the way in which the rationality of an actor might be bounded, which closely links it to the approaches based on the rational actor and the theory of bounded rationality. For a more in-depth discussion of the theory, refer to, Kahneman and Tversky (1979); Schlüter et al. (2017).

In a stochastic formulation of the given decision module, risk aversion and over- or under-weighting of probabilities could be formally expressed by modifying – an agent’s subjective – probabilities and/or departing from maximization of expected utility, e.g., to minimize the probability of some loss. However, even in the simplistic deterministic case used here, a cognitive bias can be represented. The

⁷In fact, in MoTMO, these milestones are given by a demographic evolution that is also part of the model, but for simplicity it was not included in the present setting.

Figure 2: Decision module adapted for habitual/reinforcement learning approach

decision options o_1 and o_2 are not symmetric in that owning a car allows to use other modes, but not owning a car does not allow to use one. Hence, the action of selling a car can be interpreted as corresponding to a loss.

In the respective decision module, we thus focus on the cognitive bias of loss aversion as an example. For the formalization, we suggest to introduce a loss aversion barrier LB and besides that to proceed as with the rational actor theory. LB affects the decision-making process only for agents who currently own a car, i.e. $b_t = 1$. If in the utility maximization, m^* as defined in Equation (2) equals $\{\mathbf{other}\}$, which would lead a rational agent to the decision option o_2 of not owning a car after the decision, in the case of prospect theory, the agent will only decide for this option if the utility of \mathbf{other} exceeds that of \mathbf{car} by at least the amount of LB , formally:

$$o^* = \begin{cases} o_2, & \text{IF } b_t = 1 \text{ AND } m^* = \mathbf{other} \text{ AND } u_{h_k}(\mathbf{other}) - u_{h_k}(\mathbf{car}) > LB \\ o_1, & \text{IF } b_t = 1 \text{ AND } m^* = \mathbf{car} \text{ OR } (m^* = \mathbf{other} \text{ AND } u_{h_k}(\mathbf{other}) - u_{h_k}(\mathbf{car}) \leq LB) \\ \hat{o}, & \text{IF } b_t = 0, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where \hat{o} is defined by Equation (3) as defined in Section 5.1.

5.5 Descriptive Norm

Descriptive norm theory, as originally described by Cialdini et al. (1990), suggests that individuals tend to act according to their observation of established behavior patterns of others in a specific social context. They do this rather than actively evaluating each choice, and especially when they perceive this behavior as common or typical. The theory highlights that social norms, in particular, those based on observed behavior, influence behavior by creating a sense of what is common or acceptable in a group or a society. For a more in-depth discussion of the theory, refer to Schlüter et al. (2017); Cialdini et al. (1990); Kashima et al. (2014).

In the decision module based on descriptive norm theory, the formalization is fundamentally different compared to the other approaches in that the utility of transport modes is disregarded. An agent decides on the basis of observable behavior in the population, meaning that it has to be defined

which behavior an agent is able to observe. For the formalization, let $n_{h_k} \subseteq H$ be the set of agents that agent h_k is able to observe. This set has to be specified for each agent and can be given by a – fixed or evolving – network between agents, through spatial proximity, or can simply be the set H if an agent is able to observe all agents. As an example, we assume that the behavior of the agents in the immediate surroundings has the greatest impact and introduce a network of neighbors based on geospatial proximity, e.g., allowing an agent to observe others with home locations within a given radius ρ from its own home location, i.e. $n_{h_k} = \{h_j \in H | d(l(h_j), l(h_k)) \leq \rho\}$, where d is a distance measure between locations. The definition of n and parameters like ρ need to be validated and adapted in alignment with real-world data.

In this case, as we need to consider the decisions of many agents at the same time, we include an agent index and write $o_{t,k}$ for agent h_k , dropping the h to avoid cluttering notation. An agent h_k 's decision for $t + 1$ can then be formalized as depending on the current decisions of the agents in n_{h_k} . For simplicity, we assume that n_{h_k} contains K agents and label these $1, \dots, K$. The decision is then represented as:

$$o_{t+1,k}^* = f(o_{t,1}, \dots, o_{t,K}) \quad (9)$$

where f is a function, that conveys the idea of following its inputs. E.g., it could provide the decision option that the majority in the observed group is using. In a probabilistic case, a feature that f should fulfill would be that the probability of choosing an option should increase with the number of agents in the group using that option.

Unlike all other cases discussed so far, this theory skips step 1 of the basic decision module, thus excluding an aspect considered relevant in others theories. As a result, it might be particularly interesting to first evaluate the effectiveness of this decision module during the validation process and secondly compare the results with those of other approaches.

Figure 3: Decision module adapted for descriptive norm approach

6 Discussion

Making explicit the process of defining social theory based decision modules has illustrated the necessary steps. First, the model's context must be delineated and understood – this step relates to empirical knowledge about the system under study and existing scientific literature from the field of application. Based on this context, model components (such as agents and their environment) are specified. The

definition of a decision module requires formalizing the relevant elements (such as a utility function), and a social theory in the case of theory-driven approaches. In most ABM development activities, these steps will be embedded into an iterative process consisting of definition, validation, updating the definition, further validation, and so on and so forth. For the case presented here, this process is currently in progress.

The formalizations of the five theories discussed in this work confirmed comments from the literature on the varying degree of formalization of social theories and the resulting need of interpretation for modelers. In fact, the formalization of the rational actor theory was easier than others in the sense that it could use existing mathematical descriptions as it originates in economics, where mathematical descriptions are standard, meaning that "fewer assumptions on missing elements" had to be made (Schlüter et al. 2017). Still, model-specific elements had to be defined, such as the concrete utility function to be used – as Schwarz et al. (2020) note, "even for such a highly formalized theory, several versions of the utility function exist" and the concrete choice of a function fitting a specific model context will always be up to the modeler to choose. Similarly, we had to define how exactly utility maximization translates into the selection of an option – in our case, because utility was not defined directly for the decision options, but generally this also has to be defined for cases where maximization does not yield a unique result. In other cases, however, room for modeling decisions was purposefully left open. E.g., for the descriptive norm theory, we did not specify which other agents a given agent can observe, nor which function is used to determine this agent's selection of an option. The formalization merely made the underlying structures explicit, without going all the way to a model implementation; i.e., in this case, it remained closer to the generality of the theory. The added value in mathematical notation here is that a modeler can see precisely which elements have to be specified to implement the theory. Also, properties that such a function should have can now be discussed at an abstract level rather than considering potential example functions one by one.

Having made (some) subjective decisions in translating social theories to our example model context, the resulting formal decision modules can be compared. Similarities arise in the fact that a list of elements was reusable for more than one theory (e.g., the basic utility function) and that basic structures (e.g., the two steps of evaluation and selection) are common to several theories. Here, the descriptive norm theory deviated most from all other ones, in that it skipped the step of evaluating the available options from an agent's perspective and hence makes no use of the utility function. Both bounded rationality and prospect theory can be interpreted as adding further detail to the rational actor approach. Different details can be added, and it was shown that even a single piece of detail can be formalized in different ways, meaning, e.g., that there is not a unique way of mapping changes to the rational actor approach to the steps of evaluation or selection. This illustrates that categorization of elements in social theories, such as different steps, is helpful at the general level, but even within this categorization, room for interpretation will remain when looking at concrete implementations. Finally, the habitual theory, while formalized using utility, also shows some structural difference to the rational actor and its extensions. In fact, while it determines how habits lead to maintaining a given situation, it does not specify how a new decision is taken when habits are interrupted. In practice, this means that a combination with a different decision mechanism – whether based on a different theory or chosen ad hoc – is needed to implement the habitual approach in an ABM.

In summary, we find that although the rational actor theory has been widely criticized, whether a concise theory-driven approach that is clearly superior can be elaborated remains to be seen. While some assumptions, such as complete information and utility maximization deviate from reality according to the current understanding of human behavior, their straightforward formalization is probably a main reason behind this theory's widespread use. With its more realistic ideas on how human decision-making processes are constrained by limitations in information, cognitive capacity, and time, bounded rationality theory is promising for ABMs. However, its broad definition requires significant subjective interpretation and entails a wide range of ways to bound the rational actor approach. This limits the ease of comparability of various routes taken under this theoretical heading, and hence makes it somewhat less useful in guiding theory-driven approaches. Prospect theory shares a core idea with bounded rationality theory but adds detail by identifying specific cognitive biases, such as loss aversion. It hence grounds the way in which rationality is bounded in empirical findings on human behavior and may hence help systematize different bounded rationality approaches more generally. The habitual/reinforcement learning theory emphasizes habituation and the reinforcement of behavior through positive or negative past experiences, which relates to the status quo bias in prospect theory,

while. The descriptive norm theory focuses on the role of observed behavior of others. Any of these theories will be useful for an ABM if the respective focus plays a significant role in the application under study.

For the case of long term mobility decisions laid out here, a combination of aspects from the social theories discussed is envisaged in further work. We expect to combine extensions of a rational actor approach with an influence through social norms to fill in the actual decision-making in a habitual framing which represents the fact that decisions on car ownership are not taken anew every day but rather at specific points in life and for an extended period of time.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we formalized five social theories, based on a selection made by [Schlüter et al. \(2017\)](#), where we chose a large-scale ABM on longer-term mobility decisions as the application context. This context was presented in a strongly simplified way, as the main focus was addressing the gap between theoretical understanding and explicit implementation of human behavior in computational ABM.

The explicit description of the formalization process showed where (subjective) modeling decisions had to be taken, and conditional on these decisions, facilitates and illustrates an overview and comparison of the different characteristics of the social theories. Moreover, the mathematical definitions allowed to distinguish elements that represent structural assumptions on the theories themselves and elements that can be left open to be filled in based on a model-specific context. We hope that this makes first steps towards a "common language that would be interpreted in the same way by different modelers" ([Wijermans et al. 2023](#)). The respective set of formulae together with the description of what they represent can then serve as a starting point for implementation in computational models, enabling a systematic theory-driven approach.

Limitations of the formalizations presented in this work stem, first of all, from the gap between formalization and modeling: formalizing a theory without a context would not be possible – e.g., while we could probably have left out the concrete definition of a utility function, leaving out the definition of options to be chosen from would not have allowed connecting utility maximization on modes with ownership decisions – but for any given context "mathematical modeling is part art and part science" as [Bronson and Jacobson \(1990\)](#) aptly note. Decisions taken in the formalization process might have been taken differently by other researchers. Secondly, the focus on a strongly simplified example ABM meant that some elements of theories could not be represented, such as the concept of risk that plays an important role in prospect theory but requires a notion of uncertainty. Finally, the reliance on the theories selected by [Schlüter et al. \(2017\)](#) limits the overview to these specific theories. Comprehensive formalizations of a wider range of available social theories is beyond the scope of this paper. However, these theories only briefly address, if at all, some aspects, such as temporal changes, which are particularly significant in relation to learning or habituation, or changes in the model environment and the impact on the decision-making process of an agent, and finally, interactions between agents. Formalizing further theories that focus on these aspects hence presents a possible direction for future research.

In our specific context, we see two main directions to pursue in future work: First, the provided formalizations will be implemented in a toy model application to effectively demonstrate the qualitative and quantitative differences arising from various social theories. This step aims to enhance the accessibility and comprehensibility of the work for a broader audience. Second, these formalizations will be integrated into the ABM MoTMO, using a modular approach. This integration enables the investigation of qualitative and quantitative differences between the social theories through validation with real-world data, to ultimately lead to a well-defined and suitable decision module.

In conclusion, ABMs hold great potential for addressing complex challenges in which human behavior plays a central role, such as sustainability transitions. To realize this potential, human behavior needs to be modeled with sufficient accuracy, capturing the complexity and dynamics observed in the real-world. Integrating social theories into computational models and their decision models remains a significant challenge. Currently, the effort required to implement theory-driven approaches often makes simpler designs for decision modules a more practical and advisable choice for modelers, particularly given constraints on time and resources. Clear, well-defined formalizations can improve the modeling of human behavior by establishing a common scientific language to facilitate meaningful discussions. This could support the definition of *minimal best practices* that facilitate the integration of effective

approaches into models.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Software and data availability

The Mobility Transition Model (MoTMo) is currently under development and is available here: <https://git.imp.fu-berlin.de/steffef69/momotmo>. A description of a previous (and much simpler) version of MoTMo can be found here: <https://www.comses.net/codebases/eef9e270-909b-4832-8228-c2f3a839f171/releases/1.0.0/>.

The data sources used for the development, validation, and calibration of the model are:

- *Mobilität in Deutschland* (MiD) survey studies ([BMDV 2018](#))
- Past evolution of numbers of privately owned vehicles in the study regions ([KBA 2025](#))
- Simulation output of Multi-Agent Transport Simulation (MATSim) for different study regions:
 - Open Berlin Scenario: <https://github.com/matsim-scenarios/matsim-berlin>
 - Open Lausitz Scenario: <https://github.com/matsim-scenarios/matsim-lausitz>

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stefanie Schutera: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. Sarah Wolf: Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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